

Continuity of Nonrelativistic W (wavefunction) and dW/dx from Dirac Theory?

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 18, 2024

In nonrelativistic quantum mechanics (one dimension), one enforces continuity of the wavefunction and its first spatial derivative in the case of a square well potential and in the case of one dimensional reflection-refraction.

Dirac theory of a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle, which follows from linearizing the Klein-Gordon equation, leads to a 4 vector wavefunction which, in the nonrelativistic limit, may be considered as two 2-spinors $(W, \frac{1}{2mc} \sigma \cdot p W)$, where W is the nonrelativistic wavefunction and σ a vector of Pauli matrices. In the case of one dimension, one may replace $\sigma \cdot p$ with $-i\hbar \sigma(x) d/dx$. Continuity of this two 2-spinor wavefunction automatically incorporates continuity of W and dW/dx .

In this note, we examine the reasons for this result. In particular, 2×2 Pauli matrices and a 2-vector W suffice if one only has d/dx . d/dy , d/dz partial. With d/dt partial present, one is forced to use four dimensions and 4×4 matrices which have Pauli matrices as off diagonal entries with a positive sign for the upper one and a negative for the other. This leads to coupling of the two 2-spinors (W_1, W_2) , with two equations appearing with either W_1 and $\sigma \cdot p W_2$ or vice versa. Again, it is the energy term which leads to $W_2 = \frac{1}{2mc} \sigma \cdot p W_1$, i.e. to the form $(W \text{ nonrelativistic}, dW \text{ nonrel}/dx)$ whose continuity included both W and dW/dx automatically, i.e. this continuity does not need to be added by hand as is usually done nonrelativistically.

Continuity of W nonrelativistic and dW/dx

In one dimensional nonrelativistic quantum mechanics, one enforces, by hand, continuity of W and dW/dx in the case of a square well potential (at the edge of the potential) and in one dimensional reflection-refraction at the n_1 - n_2 junction, where n is the index of refraction. One might suggest that it would be convenient if these two continuities appeared naturally as part of some more general theory. We argue that they do and this theory is Dirac's spin $\frac{1}{2}$ wave equation in the nonrelativistic limit.

Dirac Equation

The Dirac equation arises from the linearization of the second order Klein-Gordon equation:

$$-\partial_t^2 W = -\text{grad} \cdot \text{grad} W + m^2 W \quad (c=1, \hbar=1) \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{A linear form is: } (A d/dx + B d/dy + C d/dz + D d/dt) \text{ partial } W = mc W \quad ((2))$$

provided that this form multiplied by its complex conjugate transpose yields the Klein-Gordon equation.

If one only had to deal with the momentum operators, $d/dx, d/dy, d/dz$ partial, then the 3 orthogonal basis vectors e_x, e_y, e_z , could be replaced with 2×2 Pauli matrices which

anticommute. The issue, however, is the d/dt operator. As a result, one keeps the Pauli matrices, but needs 4×4 matrices with three of them having Pauli matrices as off diagonal terms, with the top matrix appearing with a plus sign and the bottom with minus. The fourth contains the 2×2 identity matrices along the diagonal, again with the first positive and the second negative. (1).

Thus, it is the d/dt operator which leads to a 4-vector wavefunction which may be broken into two 2-spinors. It is also the d/dt operator which is responsible for the Pauli matrices appearing in off-diagonal positions, if the 2×2 identity appears in the diagonal positions for the matrix of d/dt partial. Finally, it is the d/dt operator which is responsible for one Pauli matrix being positive and the other negative. It is these three features, we argue, which lead to the bottom spinor essentially being dW/dx in the nonrelativistic limit, where W is the first spinor and represents the nonrelativistic wavefunction.

To see these results (which appear in (1)) consider the following. The Pauli matrices $\sigma(x)$, $\sigma(y)$, $\sigma(x)$ anticommute and have a value of $\sigma(i)\sigma(i)=\text{identity}$ (no sum on i). Examining ((2)) from the point of view of the $d/dx, d/dy, d/dz$ partial momentum operators, one only needs these 2×2 matrices. The problem becomes anti-commutation of $d/dx, d/dy, d/dz$ partial with d/dt partial. One may retain the Pauli matrices by using them as blocks, either diagonal or off-diagonal in a 4×4 matrix. Given that $\sigma(i)\sigma(i)=\text{identity}$ (no sum on i), one needs a 2×2 matrix for d/dt whose square is also the identity. This is the 2×2 identity matrix. To have this anticommutation, one may use:

$$\begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 1 & 0 \\ \hline 0 & -1 \\ \hline \end{array} \quad \text{and} \quad \begin{array}{|c|c|} \hline 0 & \sigma(i) \\ \hline -\sigma(i) & 0 \\ \hline \end{array} \quad ((3))$$

In other words, $\sigma(i)$ appears in an off diagonal position and the top one is positive, while the bottom is negative. This means that there is a mixing of the 4-vector wavefunction which may be broken into two 2-spinors (W_1, W_2). This mixing necessarily involves the linear operators $d/dx, d/dy$ and d/dz . At this point, no nonrelativistic considerations have appeared, but we stress that it is the d/dt partial operator which is responsible for all of these features, because one only needs 2×2 Pauli matrices to ensure that $\sigma(i) d/dx(i)$ (sum on i) when multiplied by itself (or its dagger) yields the Klein-Gordon grad dot grad.

Thus, as shown in (1), the two Dirac equations for the two 2-spinors W_1, W_2 are:

$$(E-V)W_1 - c \sigma \cdot p W_2 = mc W_1 \quad ((4a))$$

$$(-\sigma \cdot p) W_1 - (E-V) W_2 = mc W_2 \quad ((4b))$$

Here E in the Klein-Gordon equation for a bound state has been replaced with $E-V$, i.e. $-id/dt W_1 = EW_1$ and $-id/dt \text{ partial } W_2 = E W_2$.

We note that the energy term and mcW_1 in ((4a)) have the same sign while in ((4b)) they have opposite signs. This is important and follows from the top Pauli matrix being positive and the

bottom negative, which also is associated with the top identity 2x2 matrix for d/dt partial being positive and the bottom, negative.

In the nonrelativistic limit, it is again the energy term which is key. The nonrelativistic approximation uses the idea that mcc (m =rest mass) is essentially the full energy and any potential and kinetic energies are insignificant. This allows one to write $E \approx mcc$ in ((4b)) and obtain:

$$(-\sigma \cdot p) W = 2 mc W \quad ((5a))$$

Inserting ((5a)) into ((4a)) yields the time-independent Schrodinger equation. Thus, W is essentially the gradient of W , the nonrelativistic wavefunction.. One solves for the nonrelativistic wavefunction W through the Schrodinger equation and then takes $\sigma \cdot \text{grad } W$ to obtain W .

In a one dimensional nonrelativistic problem, one may replace the sigma vector with $\sigma(x)$ and note that $\sigma(x)\sigma(x)=1$. In such a case, the full wavefunction is:

$$(W \text{ nonrelativistic, } \sigma(x)/2mc (-i\hbar/dx) \text{ partial } W \text{ nonrelativistic}) \quad ((6))$$

Forcing continuity of the full wavefunction in a one dimensional square well problem or a one dimensional reflection-refraction problem (for a particle with rest mass) automatically yields continuity of the wavefunction and its first spatial derivative, something that one usually has to enforce by hand.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that in one dimensional nonrelativistic mechanics, one enforces continuity of the wavefunction and its first derivative d/dx at a junction point in the square well problem and in one dimensional reflection-refraction at a n_1 - n_2 junction (n =index for refraction). These two conditions are enforced by hand.

We note that if one uses the nonrelativistic limit of the Dirac theory for spin .5 objects, then one has the full wavefunction ($W, 1/2mc \sigma(x) (-i\hbar/dx) W$), where W is the nonrelativistic wavefunction. One only solves, however, for W using the Schrodinger equation, so $1/2mc \sigma(x) (-i\hbar/dx) W$ is essentially dW/dx partial, Here $\sigma(x)$ is the Pauli x matrix. Thus, if one uses the full wavefunction and enforces its continuity (as in a square well potential or one dimensional reflection-refraction), one automatically introduces continuity of W and dW/dx partial.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Dirac_equation#:~:text=A%20further%20approximation%20gives%20the,at%20low%20energies%20and%20velocities.